

Supplementary Information

Large reductions in nutrient losses needed to avoid future coastal eutrophication across Europe

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Supplementary Text 1: Study area

We studied 594 rivers (593 basins and 8 sub-basins of the Danube River) in the European Union including the United Kingdom (EU-28) (see details in Ural-Janssen et al. (2023)). These rivers discharge into six seas/oceans namely, the Arctic Ocean, Atlantic Ocean, Baltic Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and North Sea. The Danube River includes eight sub-basins (i.e. Upstream, Drava, Sava, Tisza, Siret, Prut, Middlestream and Downstream delta) and covers 14% (797,289 km²) of the study area (5,768,449 km²) (Ural-Janssen et al., 2023).

Box S1 Summarised equations of the MARINA-Nutrients model for Europe to quantify river export of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) to European seas from diffuse and point sources (see details in Ural-Janssen et al. (2023)). Parameters are described in Box S2.

Equation		Number
$RSdif_{F.lech.ant.j} = Area_j \times Agr_{fr.j} \times EC_F \times CL_F Rnat_j$	for DON and DOP, used in Eq.1 in the paper	Eq.S1
$RSdif_{F.lech.nat.j} = Area_j \times (1 - Agr_{fr.j}) \times EC_F \times CL_F Rnat_j$	for DON and DOP, used in Eq.1 in the paper	Eq.S2
$RSdif_{DIP.wth.ant.j} = Area_j \times Agr_{fr.j} \times EC_{DIP} \times CW_{DIP} Rnat_j$	for DIP, used in Eq.1 in the paper	Eq.S3
$RSdif_{DIP.wth.nat.j} = Area_j \times (1 - Agr_{fr.j}) \times EC_{DIP} \times CW_{DIP} Rnat_j$	for DIP, used in Eq.1 in the paper	Eq.S4
$Rnat_j = Q_{nat.j} / Area_j$	used in Eq.5 in the paper	Eq.S5
$WSdif_{F.gross.j} = WSdif_{E.fe.j} + WSdif_{E.ma.j} + WSdif_{E.dep.ant.j} + WSdif_{E.fix.ant.j} + WSdif_{E.hum.uncon.j}$	for DIN, used in Eq.4 in the paper	Eq.S6
$WSdif_{F.gross.j} = WSdif_{E.fe.j} + WSdif_{E.ma.j} + WSdif_{E.dep.ant.j} + WSdif_{E.hum.uncon.j}$	for DIP, used in Eq.4 in the paper	Eq.S7
$WSdif_{F.gross.j} = WSdif_{E.fe.j} + WSdif_{E.ma.j} + WSdif_{E.hum.uncon.j}$	for DON and DOP, used in Eq.4 in the paper	Eq.S8
$WSdif_{E.hum.uncon.j} = WSdif_{E.hum.uncon.urb.j} + WSdif_{E.hum.uncon.rur.j}$		Eq.S9
$WSdif_{N.hum.uncon.urb.j} = Nexc_{hum.uncon.urb.j} \times (1 - fr_{NH3.hum})$		Eq.S10
$WSdif_{N.hum.uncon.rur.j} = Nexc_{hum.uncon.rur.j} \times (1 - fr_{NH3.hum})$		Eq.S11
$WSdif_{P.hum.uncon.urb.j} = Pexc_{hum.uncon.urb.j}$		Eq.S12
$WSdif_{P.hum.uncon.rur.j} = Pexc_{hum.uncon.rur.j}$		Eq.S13
$Nexc_{hum.uncon.urb.j} = E_{hum.j}^N \times Pop_{uncon.urb.j}$		Eq.S14
$Nexc_{hum.uncon.rur.j} = E_{hum.j}^N \times Pop_{uncon.rur.j}$		Eq.S15
$E_{hum.j}^N = I_{hum.j}^N \times 0.365$		Eq.S16
$I_{hum.j}^N = 4 + 17 \times [GDP_{ppp.j} / 68673]^{0.3}$		Eq.S17
$Pexc_{hum.uncon.urb.j} = E_{hum.j}^P \times Pop_{uncon.urb.j}$		Eq.S18
$Pexc_{hum.uncon.rur.j} = E_{hum.j}^P \times Pop_{uncon.rur.j}$		Eq.S19
$E_{hum.j}^P = E_{hum.j}^N \times (1/6)$		Eq.S20
$Nexc_{hum.con.urb.j} = E_{hum.j}^N \times Pop_{con.urb.j}$	used in Eq.7 in the paper	Eq.S21
$Nexc_{hum.con.rur.j} = E_{hum.j}^N \times Pop_{con.rur.j}$	used in Eq.8 in the paper	Eq.S22
$Pexc_{hum.con.urb.j} = E_{hum.j}^P \times Pop_{con.urb.j}$	used in Eq.7 in the paper	Eq.S23
$Pexc_{hum.con.rur.j} = E_{hum.j}^P \times Pop_{con.rur.j}$	used in Eq.8 in the paper	Eq.S24
$D_{F,j} = (1/Q_{act.j}) \times \sum_{i=1 \dots n} (Q_{act.i} \times D_{F,i})$	for DIN and DIP, used in Eq.10 in the paper	Eq.S25
$D_{DIN,i} = 0.8845 \times (h_i / \tau_{R,i})^{-0.3677}$		Eq.S26
$D_{DIP,i} = 0.85 \times [1 - \exp(-0.0807 \times 365 \times \tau_{R,i})]$		Eq.S27

$\tau_{R,i} = V_i / Q_{act,i}$		Eq.S28
$L_{DIN,j} = 0.0605 \times \ln(\text{Area}_j) - 0.0443$	for DIN and constants for DIP, used in Eq.10 in the paper	Eq.S29
$FQrem_j = 1 - (Q_{act,j}/Q_{nat,j})$	used in Eqs.10-11 in the paper	Eq.S30
${}^{juT}FE_{riv.F.outlet,jmC} = (1 - [D_{F,jmC} \times {}^{juT}A_{jmC}]) \times (1 - [L_{F,jmC} \times {}^{juT}A_{jmC}]) \times (1 - [FQrem_{jmC} \times {}^{juT}A_{jmC}])$	used in Eq.12 in the paper	Eq.S31
${}^{juT}FE_{riv.F.outlet,jdC} = (1 - [D_{F,jdC} \times {}^{juT}A_{jdC}]) \times (1 - [L_{F,jdC} \times {}^{juT}A_{jdC}]) \times (1 - [FQrem_{jdC} \times {}^{juT}A_{jdC}])$	used in Eq.12 in the paper	Eq.S32
${}^{jmT}FE_{riv.F.outlet,jdC} = (1 - [D_{F,jdC} \times {}^{jmT}A_{jdC}]) \times (1 - [L_{F,jdC} \times {}^{jmT}A_{jdC}]) \times (1 - [FQrem_{jdC} \times {}^{jmT}A_{jdC}])$	used in Eq.13 in the paper	Eq.S33
${}^{jmC}FE_{riv.F.outlet,jdC} = (1 - [D_{F,jdC} \times {}^{jmC}A_{jdC}]) \times (1 - [L_{F,jdC} \times {}^{jmC}A_{jdC}]) \times (1 - [FQrem_{jdC} \times {}^{jmC}A_{jdC}])$	used in Eq.14 in the paper	Eq.S34

Box S2 Descriptions of the abbreviations in Box S1 adjusted from Ural-Janssen et al. (2023).

Parameter	Description	Unit
y	Source	-
j	Basin (sub-basins for the Danube River)	-
i	Reservoir	-
RSdif _{F.lch.ant.j}	Inputs of nutrient form F (DON and DOP) to rivers from organic matter leaching (lch) over agricultural areas (ant) in basin j	kg N or P yr ⁻¹
RSdif _{F.lch.nat.j}	Inputs of nutrient form F (DON and DOP) to rivers from organic matter leaching (lch) over non-agricultural areas (nat) in basin j	kg N or P yr ⁻¹
RSdif _{DIP.wth.ant.j}	Inputs of DIP to rivers from P weathering (wth) in agricultural areas (ant) in basin j	kg P yr ⁻¹
RSdif _{DIP.wth.nat.j}	Inputs of DIP to rivers from P weathering (wth) in non-agricultural areas (nat) in basin j	kg P yr ⁻¹
Area _j	The drainage area of basin j	km ²
Ag _{fr.j}	Fraction of agricultural area in basin j	0-1
EC _F	Watershed export rate for nutrient form F (DON and DOP) from leaching of organic matter	kg km ⁻² yr ⁻¹
EC _{DIP}	Watershed export rate for DIP from P weathering	kg km ⁻² yr ⁻¹
CW _F	Uncalibrated export coefficient for leaching of nutrient form F (DON and DOP) from land to surface waters	-
CW _{DIP}	Uncalibrated export coefficient for weathering of DIP from land to surface waters	-
R _{nat.j}	Annual surface runoff from land to streams in basin j	m yr ⁻¹
Q _{nat.j}	Natural (nat) river discharge at the outlet of basin j, before water is taken for consumption	km ³ yr ⁻¹
WSdif _{F.gross.j}	The sum of all the inputs of nutrient form F (DIN, DON, DIP or DOP) to agricultural land in basin j	kg N or P yr ⁻¹
WSdif _{E.fe.j}	Inputs of nutrient element E (N and P) from synthetic fertilizers (fe) that are applied to agricultural land in basin j	kg N or P yr ⁻¹
WSdif _{E.ma.j}	Inputs of nutrient element E (N and P) from animal manure (ma) that is applied to agricultural land in basin j	kg N or P yr ⁻¹
WSdif _{E.dep.ant.j}	Inputs of nutrient element E (N and P) from atmospheric deposition (dep) over agricultural land (ant) in basin j	kg N or P yr ⁻¹
WSdif _{N.fix.ant.j}	Inputs of N from biological N ₂ fixation (fix) by agricultural crops (ant) in basin j	kg N yr ⁻¹
WSdif _{E.hum.uncon.j}	Inputs of nutrient element E (N and P) from excretion of population (hum) not connected to sewage systems (uncon) in basin j	kg N or P yr ⁻¹
WSdif _{E.hum.uncon.urb.j}	Inputs of nutrient element E (N and P) from excretion of urban population (urb) not connected to sewage systems (uncon) in basin j	kg N or P yr ⁻¹
WSdif _{E.hum.uncon.rur.j}	Inputs of nutrient element E (N and P) from excretion of rural population (rur) not connected to sewage systems (uncon) in basin j	kg N or P yr ⁻¹
N _{exc.hum.uncon.urb.j}	N in human excretion from urban population unconnected to sewage systems in basin j	kg N yr ⁻¹
N _{exc.hum.uncon.rur.j}	N in human excretion from rural population unconnected to sewage systems in basin j	kg N yr ⁻¹
fr _{NH3.hum}	Fraction of N losses from human excretion to the air	0-1

Parameter	Description	Unit
$P_{exc_{hum.uncon.urb.j}}$	P in human excretion from urban population unconnected to sewage systems in basin j	kg P yr ⁻¹
$P_{exc_{hum.uncon.rur.j}}$	P in human excretion from rural population unconnected to sewage systems in basin j	kg P yr ⁻¹
$E_{hum,j}^N$	Human N excretion rate in basin j	kg person ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
$I_{hum,j}^N$	Protein N intake for basin j	g N person ⁻¹ day ⁻¹
$GDP_{ppp,j}$	Annual gross domestic product at purchasing power parity	US\$ 2005 person ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
$E_{hum,j}^P$	Human P excretion rate in basin j	kg person ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
$POP_{uncon.urb.j}$	Urban population without sewage connection in basin j	People
$POP_{uncon.rur.j}$	Rural population without sewage connection in basin j	People
$N_{exc_{hum.con.urb.j}}$	N in human excretion from urban population connected to sewage systems in basin j	kg N yr ⁻¹
$N_{exc_{hum.con.rur.j}}$	N in human excretion from rural population connected to sewage systems in basin j	kg N yr ⁻¹
$P_{exc_{hum.con.urb.j}}$	P in human excretion from urban population connected to sewage systems in basin j	kg P yr ⁻¹
$P_{exc_{hum.con.rur.j}}$	P in human excretion from rural population connected to sewage systems in basin j	kg P yr ⁻¹
$POP_{con.urb.j}$	Urban population with sewage connection in basin j	People
$POP_{con.rur.j}$	Rural population with sewage connection in basin j	People
$D_{F,j}$	Fraction of nutrient form F (DIN and DIP) retained in reservoirs and (regulated) lakes in basin j	0-1
$L_{F,j}$	Fraction of nutrient form F (DIN and DIP) retained in or/and lost from water systems (e.g., denitrification) in basin j	0-1
$Q_{act,j}$	Actual (act) water discharge at the outlet of basin j after water consumption	km ³ yr ⁻¹
$juTFE_{riv.F.outlet,jmC}$ $juTFE_{riv.F.outlet,jdC}$	Fractions of nutrient form F (DIN, DON, DIP and DOP) exported from the outlet of upstream tributary (upper case: juT) to the outlets of the main channel in middlestream (lower case: jmC) and downstream (lower case: jdC) sub-basins	0-1
$jmTFE_{riv.F.outlet,jdC}$ $jmCFE_{riv.F.outlet,jdC}$	Fraction of nutrient form F (DIN, DON, DIP and DOP) exported from the outlet of middlestream subbasin with the main channel (upper case: jmC) to the outlet of the main channel in downstream (lower case: jdC) sub-basin (the outlet of the this downstream subbasin is the river mouth)	0-1
$D_{F,jmC}$ $D_{F,jdC}$	Fractions of nutrient form F (DIN and DIP) retained in reservoirs of middlestream (jmC) and downstream (jdC) sub-basins with the main channel (C). These fractions were calculated for sub-basins using equations for $D_{DIN,j}$ and $D_{DIP,j}$ from Table S1	0-1
$L_{F,jmC}$ $L_{F,jdC}$	Fractions of nutrient form F (DIN and DIP) that is lost from surface waters of middlestream (jmC) and downstream (jdC) sub-basins with the main channel (C). These fractions were calculated using the equation for $L_{DIN,j}$ and $L_{DIP,j}$ from Table S1	0-1

Parameter	Description	Unit
FQrem _{jmC} FQrem _{jdC}	Fractions of nutrient form F (generic for DIN, DON, DIP and DOP) that are lost from surface waters of middlestream (jmC) and downstream (jdC) sub-basins with the main channel (C) via water consumption. These fractions were calculated using equations for FQrem _j from Box S1.	0-1
ju ^T A _{jmC} ju ^T A _{jdC}	Drainage area (A) of the main channel (C) in middlestream (lower case: jmC) and downstream (lower case: jdC) sub-basins that exports nutrients from the outlet of upstream tributary (upper case: ju ^T). This drainage area was calculated as the fraction to the total sub-basin area.	0-1
jm ^T A _{jdC}	Drainage area (A) of the main channel (C) in downstream (lower case: jdC) sub-basin that exports nitrogen from the outlet of middlestream tributary (upper case: jm ^T). This drainage area was calculated as the fraction to the total sub-basin area.	0-1
jm ^C A _{jdC}	Drainage area (A) of the main channel (C) in the downstream (lower case: jdC) subbasin that exports nitrogen from the outlet of middlestream main channel (upper case: jm ^C). This drainage area was calculated as the fraction to the total sub-basin area.	0-1

Table S1 Main characteristics and approaches of the baseline (SSP5-RCP8.5) scenario for 2050, and changes relative to current situation (2017-2020) in Europe.

Characteristics	2017-2020	2050 based on SSP5-RCP8.5	Change	Approaches
Population (person)	547,997,738	647,278,070	+18%	Urban, rural and total populations per basin for 2020 are derived from Ural-Janssen et al. (2023) and for 2050 are derived from Stokal et al. (2021) based on the SSP5 scenario. Stokal et al. (2021) assumes high urbanization (e.g., increasing number of people living in cities and people with sewage connections) and moderate improvement in wastewater treatment plants (e.g., shifting from secondary to tertiary treatment).
urban population	419,695,198	580,757,907	+38%	
rural population	128,302,540	66,520,163	-48%	
Sewage connection rates (0-1)		high		
Wastewater treatment rates (0-1)		moderate improvement		
GDP (US\$ capita ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	27,098	69,843	+158%	Average GDP per basin is calculated as a function of the GDP and population per basin. The GDP data is derived from Stokal et al. (2021) for 2010 representing the current and for 2050 based on the SSP5 scenario.
Agricultural area (cropland, grassland, area set aside and fallow) (km ²)	2,205,561	2,242,472	~ +2%	Data on agricultural area is derived from the MITERRA-Europe model for 2017 at NUTS2 scale (Duan et al., 2021), and projected for 2050 per basin as a function of the percent changes between 2015-2050 in the IMAGE model based on the SSP5-RCP8.5 scenario (Beusen et al., 2022). Beusen et al. (2022) considers the same trajectories for land use between 2015-2020 based on SSP2 for all SSPs, and the scenarios start to differ from 2021 onwards.
N inputs to agricultural land	29.2 Tg N yr ⁻¹ 132 kg N ha ⁻¹	31.2 Tg N yr ⁻¹ 139 kg N ha ⁻¹	+7%	Data on N inputs to agricultural land is derived from the MITERRA-Europe model for 2017 at NUTS2 scale (Duan et al., 2021), and projected for 2050 per basin as a function of the percent changes between 2015-2050 in the IMAGE model based on the SSP5-RCP8.5 scenario (Beusen et al., 2022).
N inputs to non-agricultural land	5.1 Tg N yr ⁻¹	5.5 Tg N yr ⁻¹	+6%	Data on N inputs to non-agricultural land is derived from the IMAGE model for 2015 at 0.5° grids, and projected for 2050 per basin as a function of the percent changes between 2015-2050 in the IMAGE model based on the SSP5-RCP8.5 scenario (Beusen et al., 2022).
P inputs to agricultural land	1.7 Tg P yr ⁻¹ 7.9 kg P ha ⁻¹	1.8 Tg P yr ⁻¹ 8 kg P ha ⁻¹	+3%	Data on P inputs to agricultural land is derived from the MITERRA-Europe model for 2017 at NUTS2 scale (Duan et al., 2021), and projected for 2050 per basin as a function of the percent changes between 2015-2050 in the IMAGE model based on the SSP5-RCP8.5 scenario (Beusen et al., 2022).

Table S2 Description of how model inputs are processed to basins for the MARINA-Nutrients model for Europe. Numbers indicate the equation numbers in Box S1.

Numbers	Description of how model inputs are processed for 2050
Eqs.S1-S2 and Eq.1 in the paper	Organic matter (e.g., litter, decomposition products, organic residues) can bring dissolved organic nutrients via precipitation and runoff to surface waters (Gmach et al., 2020). Inputs of N (DON) and P (DOP) to rivers from the leaching of organic matter from agricultural and non-agricultural soils (kg N or P yr^{-1} per basin) were calculated for 2050 as a function of agricultural/non-agricultural area (km^2) in basin, watershed export rates for leaching of organic matter (EC_{DON} and EC_{DOP} , $\text{kg km}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), uncalibrated export coefficients for leaching of nutrients from land to waters and annual surface runoff from land to streams ($\text{CL}_F \times \text{Rnat}_j$, calculated using runoff values, unitless). Basin area was derived from Strokal et al. (2016). The fraction of agricultural area in basin ($\text{Agr}_{\text{fr},j}$, 0-1) was calculated for 2050 by dividing the agricultural area estimated for 2050 by basin area. The coefficients for organic matter leaching: $\text{EC}_{\text{DON}} = 280 \text{ kg km}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and $\text{EC}_{\text{DOP}} = 15 \text{ kg km}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ were derived from Mayorga et al. (2010). For $\text{Rnat}_j \geq 0.1 \text{ m}$, uncalibrated export coefficient CL_F for DON and DOP was considered as 1.0, and for $\text{Rnat}_j < 0.1 \text{ m}$, 0.9, as these coefficients gave globally comparable results for DON and DOP leaching to surface waters from agricultural areas. Rnat_j was calculated for 2050 by dividing the natural discharge with the basin area.
Eqs.S3-S4 and Eq.1 in the paper	Inputs of P to rivers from the weathering of P-contained minerals from agricultural and non-agricultural areas (kg N or P yr^{-1} per basin) were calculated for 2050 as a function of agricultural/non-agricultural area (km^2) in basin, watershed export rates for DIP weathering (EC_{DIP} , $\text{kg km}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), uncalibrated export coefficient for weathering of DIP from land to waters and annual surface runoff from land to streams ($\text{CL}_{\text{DIP}} \times \text{Rnat}_j$, calculated using runoff values, unitless). $\text{EC}_{\text{DIP}} = 26 \text{ kg km}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ was derived from Mayorga et al. (2010). For $\text{Rnat}_j \geq 0.1 \text{ m}$, CL_{DIP} was considered as 0.4, and for $\text{Rnat}_j < 0.1 \text{ m}$, 0.2, as these coefficients gave globally comparable results for DIP weathering from agricultural areas.
Eqs.S6-S8 and Eq.2 in the paper	Inputs of N and P to land from synthetic fertilizer application to agricultural land (kg N or P yr^{-1} per basin) were calculated for 2050 as a function of the current (2017) synthetic fertilizer application derived from the MITERRA-Europe (Duan et al., 2021) and the percent change in the synthetic fertilizer application to agricultural land between 2015-2050 based on the SSP5 scenario derived from the IMAGE model (Beusen et al., 2022).
Eqs.S6-S8 and Eq.2 in the paper	Inputs of N and P to land from animal manure (applied to agricultural land and deposited on land during grazing) (kg N or P yr^{-1} per basin) were calculated for 2050 as a function of the current (2017) animal manure derived from the MITERRA-Europe (Duan et al., 2021) and the percent change in the animal manure recycled to agricultural land between 2015-2050 based on the SSP5 scenario derived from the IMAGE model (Beusen et al., 2022).
Eqs.S6-S7 and Eq.2 in the paper	Inputs of N and P to land from atmospheric deposition on agricultural land (kg N or P yr^{-1} per basin) were calculated for 2050 as a function of the current (2017) atmospheric deposition derived from the MITERRA-Europe (Duan et al., 2021) and the percent change in the atmospheric deposition on agricultural land between 2015-2050 based on the SSP5 scenario derived from the IMAGE model (Beusen et al., 2022).

Numbers	Description of how model inputs are processed for 2050
Eq.S6 and Eq.2 in the paper	Inputs of N to land from biological N ₂ fixation by agricultural crops (kg N yr ⁻¹ per basin) were calculated for 2050 as a function of the current (2017) biological N ₂ fixation derived from the MITERRA-Europe (Duan et al., 2021) and the percent change in the biological N ₂ fixation by agricultural crops between 2015-2050 based on the SSP5 scenario derived from the IMAGE model (Beusen et al., 2022).
Eqs.S6-S13 and Eq.2 in the paper	Inputs of N and P to land from the excretion of population unconnected to sewer systems (kg N or P yr ⁻¹ per basin) were calculated for 2050 as a function of unconnected population (people) and the rates of human excretion for N and P (kg cap ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹) in basins based on the SSP5 scenario. Total, urban and rural population unconnected to sewage systems were derived from Strokal et al. (2021) for 2050 based on the SSP5 scenario (people per basin). We used the approach of Ural-Janssen et al. (2023) by considering there is no direct discharge of the untreated wastewater from population (urban and rural) not connected to sewage systems in Europe, and the unconnected human waste is lost to rivers through land. Therefore, we considered the untreated human wastewater as a diffuse source for the nutrient inputs to rivers through land (i.e. $WSdif_{N,hum.uncon,j}$ and $WSdif_{P,hum.uncon,j}$). The fraction of N loss to air from human excretion not connected to sewage systems $fr_{NH3,hum} = 0.24$ was derived from Ma et al. (2010).
Eq.2 in the paper	Inputs of N to land from atmospheric deposition on non-agricultural land (kg N yr ⁻¹ per basin) were derived from the IMAGE model for 2015 (current) and for 2050 based on the SSP5 scenario (Beusen et al., 2022).
Eq.2 in the paper	Inputs of N to land from biological N ₂ fixation by natural vegetation (kg N yr ⁻¹ per basin) were derived from the IMAGE model for 2015 (current) and for 2050 based on the SSP5 scenario (Beusen et al., 2022).
Eq.4 in the paper	Exports of N and P from agricultural land by crop harvesting and animal grazing (kg N or P yr ⁻¹ per basin) were calculated for 2050 as a function of the current (2017) exports of N and P derived from the MITERRA-Europe (Duan et al., 2021) and the percent change in the exports of N and P from agricultural land by crop harvesting and animal grazing between 2015-2050 based on the SSP5 scenario derived from the IMAGE model (Beusen et al., 2022).
Eqs.S5, S25 and S30	Natural water discharges were derived from Variable Infiltration Capacity (VIC) macroscale hydrological model for 2010 as current (by averaging the data over 30 years of the period 1980-2010 to avoid the influence of climate extremes) and for 2050 (van Vliet et al., 2016) and used to calculate inputs of nutrients to rivers. Actual water discharges were calculated for 2010 as current (see details in (Ural-Janssen et al., 2023)) and for 2050 by using the water consumption projections for 2050 based on SSP5-RCP8.5 scenario from Khan et al. (2022). First, the annual water consumption data for 2050 was derived from Khan et al. (2022) at 0.5° resolution (km ³ yr ⁻¹ per grid cell). Total water consumption (Q _{rem}) was the sum of six sectors, namely irrigation, livestock, domestic, electricity, manufacturing and mining (km ³ yr ⁻¹) (Khan et al., 2022). Second, the gridded Q _{rem} data was aggregated for basin over the corresponding grids (km ³ yr ⁻¹ per basin). Third, the actual discharges (Q _{act}) were quantified by subtracting Q _{rem} from the natural discharge Q _{nat} for 2050 (km ³ yr ⁻¹ per basin). The Q _{act,j} ≤ 0 was considered as “0.036 km ³ yr ⁻¹ ”, as this was the lowest Q _{act,j} value per basin among the current actual water discharges (2010).
Eqs.S1-S5 and Eq.5 in the paper	Surface runoff (m yr ⁻¹ per basin) was calculated by dividing the natural discharge for 2050 (Q _{nat} , km ³ yr ⁻¹ per basin) with the area of basin (km ²) following the approach of Strokal et al. (2016).
Eqs.2, 4-5 in the paper	Uncalibrated approach was used to calculate the export fraction of nutrients entering rivers of basin (FE _{ws,F,j} , 0-1) and the fraction of nutrients applied to agricultural land that remained in soils of basin (G _{F,j} , 0-1) following Li et al. (2022). In this approach, the world basins were clustered based on the climate zones from FAO (2007) to calculate the fractions of nutrients retained in soils after crop harvesting and animal grazing (G _{F,j}). Among the European basins (593 basins and 8 sub-basins of the Danube River), 223 basins were in subtropic/tropic

Numbers	Description of how model inputs are processed for 2050
	<p>zones and assumed to have a rather wet climate, and 378 basins were in other temperature zones and assumed to have a rather dry climate (Li et al., 2022). Based on the uncalibrated approach of Li et al. (2022):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If $R_{nat,j} \geq 0.1 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$, $FE_{ws,DIN,j} = 0.9 \times R_{nat,j}$ and if $R_{nat,j} < 0.1 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$, $FE_{ws,DIN,j} = 0.8 \times R_{nat,j}$ ○ If $R_{nat,j} \geq 0.1 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$, $FE_{ws,DON,j} = 0.02 \times R_{nat,j}$ and if $R_{nat,j} < 0.1 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$, $FE_{ws,DON,j} = 0.01 \times R_{nat,j}$ ○ If $R_{nat,j} \geq 0.1 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$, $FE_{ws,DIP,j} = 0.15 \times R_{nat,j}$ and if $R_{nat,j} < 0.1 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$, $FE_{ws,DIP,j} = 0.1 \times R_{nat,j}$ ○ If $R_{nat,j} \geq 0.1 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$, $FE_{ws,DOP,j} = 0.02 \times R_{nat,j}$ and if $R_{nat,j} < 0.1 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$, $FE_{ws,DOP,j} = 0.01 \times R_{nat,j}$ ○ Any of $FE_{ws,F,j} > 0.9$ was assumed that equal to 0.9. ○ If $G_{F,j} < 0$, $G_{F,j}$ was validated as 0.05 for the basins in subtropic/tropic zones, and as 0.1 for the basins in other temperature zones.
Eqs.S14-S15, S18-S19, S21-S24 and Eqs.3, 6-9 in the paper	Total, urban and rural population projections (people per basin) and sewer connection rates (0-1 per basin) were derived from Strokal et al. (2021) for 2050 based on the SSP5 scenario.
Eq.S17	Data on gross domestic product at purchasing power parity (GDPppp, US\$2005 person ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ per basin) was derived from Strokal et al. (2021) for 2050 based on the SSP5 scenario.
Eqs.S16 and S20	Excretion or consumption rates of N and P per person (kg person ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ per basin) were calculated for 2050 as a function of the GDPppp following the approach of Van Drecht et al. (2009). The consumption rate of P in detergents (i.e. laundry and washing) (kg P person ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ per basin) was derived from Strokal et al. (2021) for 2050 based on the SSP5 scenario.
Eqs.S21-24 and Eqs.7-8 in the paper	Fractions of N and P removal in wastewater treatment systems (the same for both urban and rural, 0-1 per basin) were derived from Strokal et al. (2021) for 2050 based on the SSP5 scenario.
Eq.9 in the paper	<p>Fractions of nutrient form F (DIN, DON, DIP or DOP) entering rivers from point source ($FE_{pnt,F,hum.con,j}$, 0-1 per basin) were derived from Mayorga et al. (2010) as 0.14, 1 and 0.01 for DON, DIP and DOP, respectively. For DIN, the Eq. 9 in the paper is used:</p> $FE_{pnt,DIN,hum.con,j} = 0.485 + 0.225 \times (hw_{frem,N,j} / 0.86)$ <p>where 0.485 is the fraction of total N (TN) in sewage effluents that is DIN without treatment, 0.225 is the maximum increase in DIN/TN ratio that can be achieved during treatment, $hw_{frem,N}$ is N removal in wastewater treatment systems of each basin, and 0.86 is the maximum observed value for N treatment for Europe for 2050 based on the SSP5 scenario.</p>
Eqs.S25-S29 and Eq.10 in the paper	Data on the characteristics of reservoirs and (regulated) lakes was derived from HydroLAKES Project to calculate current nutrient retentions in rivers (Messenger et al., 2016). $Q_{act,i}$ is actual water discharge for reservoir i (km ³ yr ⁻¹) and derived from Messenger et al. (2016). No change in the characteristics of reservoirs and (regulated) lakes was assumed for 2050. The fraction of DIN retained in reservoir i ($D_{DIN,i}$, 0-1) was calculated by following the approach of Strokal et al. (2016). H_i is depth of reservoir I (m) and derived from Messenger et al. (2016). $\tau_{R,i}$ is water residence time for reservoir i (year) (Strokal et al., 2016). V_i is volume of reservoir i (km ³ yr ⁻¹) and derived from Messenger et al. (2016). The nutrient retentions of individual reservoirs were averaged for basins using the actual water discharges at the outlets of the basins

Numbers	Description of how model inputs are processed for 2050
	<p>(Strokal et al., 2016). The maximum value of $D_{DIN,j}$ was set as 0.965 as this was the maximum value for the basins used to calibrate parameters (Strokal et al., 2016).</p> <p>The fraction of DIN retained in reservoir i ($D_{DIP,i}$, 0-1) was calculated by following the approach of Strokal et al. (2016). The maximum value of $D_{DIP,j}$ was set as 0.85 following the approach of Strokal et al. (2016).</p> <p>The fraction of DIN retained in and/or lost from water systems (e.g., denitrification) in basin j ($L_{DIN,j}$, 0-1) was calculated as a function of basin area (Strokal et al., 2016). The fitted coefficients 0.0605 and 0.0443 in the equation were derived from Strokal et al. (2016). The maximum value of $L_{DIN,j}$ was set as 0.65 following the approach of Strokal et al. (2016). The fraction of DIP retained in and/or lost from water systems (e.g., sedimentation) in basin j ($L_{DIP,j}$, 0-1) was set as 0.9 for dry rivers having runoff of less than 0.1 m yr^{-1} and as 0.5 for the rest of the rivers following the approach of Strokal et al. (2016).</p>
Eqs.15-18 in the paper	<p>Dissolved Silica loads (Mg yr^{-1}) per basin were derived from the Global <i>NEWS2</i> model for 2050 based on the Global Orchestration scenario (Seitzinger et al., 2010) as this scenario was the closest option to our baseline scenario. First, the DSi loads (Mg yr^{-1}) per basin were selected by using the spatial data in two steps: (1) matching the river mouths by coordinates (i.e. longitude and latitude of the river mouths from the Global <i>NEWS2</i> and MARINA-Nutrients models) and (2) matching the remaining river mouths based on the shortest distance between the river mouths from the Global <i>NEWS2</i> and MARINA-Nutrients models. Second, the DSi loads were converted from Mg yr^{-1} to $\text{kg km}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$ by dividing with the basin area (km^2) and 365 (day yr^{-1}) for unit conversion. Third, the limiting nutrient was determined based on the N:P ratio (when TN:TP ratio > 16, P is the limiting nutrient, and when TN:TP ratio < 16, N is limiting) (Billen & Garnier, 2007). Fourth, the maximum allowable river exports of nutrients were calculated by following the back-casting approach of (Li et al., 2019) for 2050 based on the SSP5-RCP8.5 scenario ($\text{kg C-eq. km}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$). Based on the limiting nutrient (N or P), the N-ICEP and P-ICEP equations were used for back-casting the maximum allowable river export of N and P for 2050 based on the ICEP = 0 (with an uncertainty range of -1 and +1) ($\text{kg C-eq. km}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$).</p>

Figure S1 Future (2050) river export of phosphorus by source to the European seas based on the SSP5-RCP8.5 scenario. (a) River export of dissolved inorganic phosphorus (DIP, Gg P yr⁻¹). (b) River export of dissolved organic phosphorus (DOP, Gg P yr⁻¹). SSP5 is short for Shared Socio-economic Pathway 5 (fossil fueled development) and RCP8.5 is short for Representative Concentration Pathways (high-end climate change). Source: MARINA-Nutrients model for Europe (Section 2.1).

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